

Assessment on Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Secondary School Facilities in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined Assessment on Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Secondary School Facilities in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State, Nigeria. Two specific objectives, two research questions were raised to guide the study. The study employed a descriptive research survey research design. The research instrument used for this study was self-designed questionnaire. The content and face validity were ascertained by psychologist, guidance and counselling experts. A reliability co-efficient of 0.83 was obtained using split half method. The population of the study consists of all Principals and Teachers in Dala Educational Zone, during the 2023/2024 academic session. Eighty-three principals constitute the sample size of the study. Two research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The study concludes that infrastructural facilities were not adequately provided and properly maintained among Secondary Schools in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State. The study recommended that infrastructural facilities should be provided and maintained among public secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone of Kano State.

Keywords: Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Facilities'.

Introduction

There is growing concern among education stakeholder and practitioners about the present poor state of infrastructural facilities available for teaching and learning in secondary schools across the country (Nigeria). There are calls for the need to re-vamp the educational sector to address the concerns of the citizenry and comply with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). These calls, gave rise to the current educational reforms of the Federal Government of Nigeria. Gana (2015) revealed that facilities and resources for teaching and learning in schools are grossly inadequate and sometimes inappropriate. This reveals the setbacks of our educational system. In the same vein, it is observed by Nwadiani (2000), observed that the facilities are not only over utilized, they are also poorly maintained. Educational facilities refer to non-human and non-financial resources. They include movable and immovable materials, which are used for teaching and learning facilities. They are synonymous with school physical facilities, school materials resources, school plant and school facilities (Abdulkarim and Fassasi, 2010). Moreover, provision of educational facilities involves the supply of all necessary learning materials, which enable a skilful teacher to achieve a level of instructional effectiveness that far exceed what is possible when they are not provided (Costaldi 1997, as cited in Gana 2015).

Adegboyeje (2000) stated that, utilization is the degree or extent to which an item has been put into effective use. According to him, various degrees of utilization include non-utilization, underutilization, maximum utilization, optimum

utilization and overutilization. In this regard, utilization of facilities for teaching has to do with judicious harnessing of teaching facilities for the achievement of educational objectives. Saba, (2006) defines maintenance as the act of taking good care of tools and equipment to prolong its life-span and to prevent it from sudden breakdown. Jerret, (2000) in Saba, (2006) sees maintenance as a process whereby machines are constantly checked and faults rectified to avoid any loss in man hours and boost production.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to Assessment on Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Secondary School Facilities in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. Assess the mean response on the extent of provision, utilization and maintenance of infrastructural facilities among Secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State.
2. assess the mean response on the extent of Provision, Utilization and maintenance of welfare facilities among Secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the mean response on the extent of infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and maintenance among secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State?
2. What is the mean response on the extent of Provision, Utilization and maintenance of welfare facilities among Secondary Schools in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State?

Research Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The target population of the study is made eighty-three (83) principals from Dala zone Kano State, Nigeria. All eighty-three principals were purposely selected as sample sizes for the study as recommended by Kreccie and Morgan. Because the whole population was used as sample of the study. The name of the questionnaire was Assessment on Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Secondary School Facilities in Dala Educational which was designed by the researchers for data collection from respondents' opinion. Seventy-nine copies of questionnaire were received and used for the analysis in order to find the results. The respondents' opinions were rated inform of strongly agree (4) agree (3) disagree (2) and strongly disagree (1) as an instrument for data collection of the study. The instrument was validated by three expert and the reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained. The researchers administered the questionnaires to the respondents, the seventy-nine (79) questionnaires were returned. The data collected were coded into statistical package of social sciences (SPSS), 25. The package was used to calculate mean and standard deviation of response from respondents.

Research Question 1

Research Question One: What is the mean response on the extent of infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and maintenance among secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State?

Table 1: Mean rating and Standard deviation oninfrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State.

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	There is adequate provision, utilize and maintenance toilet in our school.	79	3.28	1.22	Agreed
2	I.C.T. facilities were provided utilize and maintenance in our school.	79	1.08	1.215	Disagreed
3	Pipe borne water supply provided in our school and utilize.	79	3.47	1.219	Agreed
4	Medical center was fully equipped with facilities medicine are utilize and maintain on our school.	79	1.76	1.238	Disagreed
5	Recreational facilities are provided utilize and maintain in our school.	79	1.62	1.234	Disagreed
6	Internet facilities were provided, utilize and maintain in our school.	79	1.32	1.96	Disagreed

Grand Total	79	2.1	Disagree
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Source: Field study 2024

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 revealed that all items of the variable of on infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria were having a mean score of below 3.0. The mean scores of infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria ranging from 1.08 to 3.28. The grand mean of infrastructural facilities provides, utilized and maintenance is 2.1 which is below the benchmark of revised four point scale. The results indicate that the respondents Disagreed with statements of infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: What is the mean response on the extent of Utilization and maintenance of welfare facilities among Secondary Schools in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation on welfarefacilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State.

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	Promotion and advancement are provided regularly for the teachers	79	3.42	0.76	Agreed
2	In service training are allowed for all teaching and non-teaching staff.	79	3.10	0.83	Agreed
3	Car loan is provided for the teachers in the school.	79	3.00	0.90	Agreed
4	Reward is also provided for the hardworking teachers in the school	79	3.28	0.97	Agreed
5	Computers are provided for both teaching and non-teaching staff in our school.	79	3.32	1.86	Agreed
Grand Total		79	3.22		Agreed

Source: Field study, 2024.

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 revealed that all items of the variable Welfare facilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria, had a mean score of above 3.0. This means score of welfare facilities ranging from 3.00 to 3.42. The grand mean of welfare facilities is 3.22 which is above the benchmark of revised four-point scale. The results indicate that the respondents agreed with statements of welfarefacilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question 1 indicate that the respondents disagreed with statements of infrastructural facilities provide, utilize and maintenance in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria. This is in line with finding Gujar and Malik (2007) that if there are necessary facilities that will facilitate the training of child are not available, the teaching and learning process cannot be successfully carried out. Khan and Iqbal (2012), found out that excellent school facilities are basic ingredients for successful learning and for achieving the target and improving literacy rate of a country.

The finding of the research question 2 indicates that that the respondents agreed with statements of welfare facilities provision, utilize and maintenance in Dala zone of Kano state, Nigeria. This in line with finding of the findings also indicated there was a strong inadequate utilization of infrastructural teaching/learning, Welfare, recreational and game facilities in Secondary Schools in Dala Educational Zone. This was in line with findings of Adegboyeje (2000), in which he stated that utilization is the degree or extent to which an item has been put into effective use. According to him various degrees of utilization include non-utilization, underutilization maximum utilization and over utilization. Non-utilization occurs when facilities is used more than its capacity.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study the study concluded that there were no infrastructural and ware fare facilities were not adequately provided adequately utilized and maintained among secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone Kano State.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this research the following recommendations were made: -

1. Infrastructural facilities should be provided adequately utilized and maintained to make teaching and learning more effective in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone.
2. Welfare facilities should be provided and properly maintained for motivation and the overall attainment of education goals in secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone Kano State

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